

ISic0262

I.Sicily inscription 0262

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

Barratina Tower - acqueduct

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Aquae

2. Corneliae

3. ductus

4. p(edes) XX

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285210

EDR 127142

EDCS 10900684

Bibliography

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